

Grant agreement no.	101138451
Project acronym	PERSEPHONE
Project full title	Autonomous Exploration and Extraction of Deep Mineral Deposits
Dissemination level	PU – Public
Date of Delivery	11.12.2024
Deliverable Number	D10.4
Deliverable Name	Dissemination and communication plan
AL / Task related	T10.1, T10.6, T10.7, T11.1, T11.6, T11.7
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Reviewer	Anton Koval (LTU); Pär-Erik Martinsson (LTU)
Keywords	Dissemination and communication plan

Abstract

The DC plan outlines the objectives, target groups, timeline, existing channels and tools, quantitative indicators, and evaluation parameters. Its goal is to disseminate the results and findings of the PERSEPHONE project to a broad audience, including companies and organizations interested in pioneering technologies that advance the EU mining industry, autonomous systems, and integrated near-mine exploration capabilities for accessing deep deposits of critical raw materials. The plan will be reviewed, evaluated, and updated at regular intervals to ensure alignment with the project's progress. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will be used to measure the success of these activities throughout the project's duration.

History of Changes

Version	Date	Reason of change
0.1 (draft)	24 Oct 2024	The initial draft of the document was distributed between PERSEPHONE project partners to review.
0.9	05 Dec 2024	DCP version for the final review with all the partners' inputs
1.0	11 Dec 2024	Final version of the document

Executive summary

This document constitutes deliverable D10.4, the “Dissemination and Communication Plan,” for the Horizon Europe project titled “Autonomous Exploration and Extraction of Deep Mineral Deposits” (acronym: PERSEPHONE; Grant Agreement no: 101138451). It is based on the conditions outlined in the Grant Agreement and its annexes, as signed by the European Commission.

The plan outlines the general principles, tools, and target groups for the DC activities, coordinating all messages to various audiences while measuring their impact. The dissemination and communication efforts aim to enhance the visibility of the project results and foster discussions with diverse stakeholders.

As a living document, the DC Plan will be continuously expanded and monitored throughout the project's duration.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under the Grant Agreement No.101138451

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1 Abbreviations

DC	DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION
GA	GRANT AGREEMENT
KPI	KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

2 Introduction

This deliverable presents the PERSEPHONE project's Dissemination and Communication (DC) activities, detailing planned actions in line with the Grant Agreement objectives. The DC Plan outlines core principles, tools, and target audiences, ensuring consistent messaging across various groups while monitoring impact. These activities aim to enhance project visibility and foster engagement with diverse stakeholders.

As a living document, the DC Plan is continuously updated to reflect project developments, with four scheduled reports (see Table 1) documenting its progress and updates.

Table 1: Timetable of the dissemination and communication plan releases

Version	Publication date	Change
1.0		First version of the DC plan at M6

3 Dissemination and communication strategy

The dissemination and communication strategy aims to share the project's findings and results strategically and effectively, using dedicated communication tools. Initially, dissemination activities focus on promoting the PERSEPHONE project to a broad audience; subsequent steps work to enhance the visibility of project results and foster discussions with various stakeholders.

3.1 PERSEPHONE in short

Full title	AUTONOMOUS EXPLORATION AND EXTRACTION OF DEEP MINERAL DEPOSITSD
Horizon Europe Call	HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01
Start date	01 January 2024
Duration	36 Months
Type	Research and Innovation Action
Budget	4 993 125,47 €
Coordinator	Luleå University of Technology
Contact	geonik@ltu.se
Website	https://www.persephone-mining.eu/

3.1.1 Objectives of PERSEPHONE

PERSEPHONE is aiming to address these challenges by developing of the pioneering technologies for pushing the limits of EU mining industry and embodiment of autonomous and integrated near mine exploration capability to access deep deposits of critical raw materials through hard-to-reach deep and abandoned mines. The overall concept and vision of PERSEPHONE will be achieved by reducing the size of mining machines currently adapted to the human scale and embedding autonomy for risk-aware navigation and full digitalization of the extraction process by digital twin creation and key enabling technologies validation at TRL 5. Additionally, PERSEPHONE is introducing completely novel approaches in online near mine exploration core analysis and overall integration of related data analytics to the mine expansion. Thus, PERSEPHONE allows to foster green transition by reducing the cost and waste generated from deep-mining operations and foster the vision of zero human presence in highly hazardous areas. These will allow to achieve PERSEPHONE's overall goal to digitalize and automate extraction value chain by creation of new concepts of energy-efficient autonomous drilling machines with advanced perception capabilities for navigation, face drilling, and core extraction, which will enable data-driven digital twin creation and geological modelling for further enhanced decision support and optimal extraction planning.

3.1.2 Expected results

PERSEPHONE is an RIA action which will produce technologies that can be further commercially exploited. The project is expected to deliver the following Key Exploitable Results (KERs) that will be generated from the technical activities in WPs 2 – 9.

- Deep mineral exploration drilling systems
- Technologies for accurate long hole drilling
- Energy-efficient ore extraction processes
- Real-time rock characterization for targeted underground drilling
- Computer aided excavation planning
- Autonomous path planning in deep SubT environments
- Precise navigation and positioning for autonomous drilling
- Risk and traversability assessment in deep mines
- Multi-machine coordination for mapping and localization
- Precise autonomous drilling using onboard sensors
- LIBS based analysis of the chemical composition of orebody
- Spectral camera-based assessment of chemical composition of the ore body
- Non-invasive assessment of structural properties of mining face
- Data-driven Geo-modelling
- Geo-model-based investment plans and future extraction
- Upstream downstream integration methods
- Data-driven planning of mining works
- Efficient management and comprehensive extraction of mineral resources aligned with sustainable development
- Digital Twin for full digitalization of the extraction process

3.1.3 Overall approach

The well-developed infrastructure is a synergy of industries that foster economic growth and bring better quality of life. Presently the EU economy is recovering from the coronavirus crisis. For that was introduced the NextGenerationEU plan aiming to make stronger, greener and more resilient European economy and to create new job opportunities. The Mining sector plays an important role in the European Union economy by supplying its production industries with key metals and minerals¹. The global mining automation market is projected to be worth USD 4.03 billion in 2025, growing at a CAGR of 8.6% from 2019². The driving force behind it is to make hazardous mining environment safer and sustainable. For its growth technology becomes a critical factor for manufacturers and industry is demanding a large-scale adoption of robotics and automation technologies and smart materials to enhance operational efficiency and human safety.

¹ https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/raw-materials/areas-specific-interest/critical-raw-materials_en

² <https://www.globenewswire.com/news-release/2021/07/12/2261471/0/en/Mining-Automation-Market-Size-is-Predicted-to-Touch-USD-4-03-Billion-by-2025-at-an-8-6-CAGR-Report-by-Market-Research-Future-MRFR.html>

3.1.4 Consortium

PERSEPHONE consists of two world leading mining companies (GM & KGHM); two mining assisting companies in-terms of advanced technology and digitization tools (EPI & MRP); five research institutes and a SME covering various aspects related to mining like mechanical design, services, geology, autonomy, and sensor technology (CUP, GSB, LTU, DTU, SPE, UPAT, & SPE); and a nonprofit organisation (INTRAW) from different countries within Europe and South Africa (MRP). The proposed consortium brings together synergistic and interdisciplinary research strategies in non-competitive positions, each with a specific role to play in the proposed multidisciplinary research directions as well as for the exploitation of the results, without duplication of efforts or commercial conflicts. The richness and synergistic character of the expertise in PERSEPHONE is outlined below:

LTU with the participation of two Departments (Department of Computer Science, Electrical and Space Engineering and Department of Civil, Environmental and Natural Resources Engineering) will perform ground-breaking research in the field of trusted autonomy for the next generation of mining robotics as well as support geo-modelling, and upstream and downstream data integration and interoperability in mining studies, to properly address the major cornerstones of the PERSEPHONE vision. The robotics & artificial intelligence group at LTU, the leader of this proposal, is among the best field robotics teams in Europe whose team won the 2nd Challenge of the DARPA SubT competition, which is also heavily working in the field of autonomy in extreme subterranean environments in terms of path planning, autonomous visual navigation, localization, mapping and traversability.

EPI is one of the world-leading companies developing and providing various innovative and safe mining infrastructures ranging from rock excavators, drill rigs, to construction equipment and tools for both surface and underground mining applications. They bring in a wide variety of expertise in drill rigs, excavators and their autonomy stacks, as well as exploration mining applications.

GM is a private mining company from Greece and ranks among the top magnesia producers and exporters in the world. They will provide expertise in exploration, drilling, and excavation aspect within the project and have access to the underground abandoned mine which provides a unique advantage with regards to the validation of the concepts proposed within the project.

INTRAW is a not-for-profit, independent entity that provides specialised support on raw materials cooperation, diplomacy, and foresight, and helps organisations along the minerals value chain while improving their sustainability performance. They are active in the UN Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) Expert Group on Resource Management (responsible for the development of the UNFC and UNRMS) and bring an extensive body of knowledge in cross-sectoral policies covering economic, environmental and social dimensions.

LPRC is an affiliated entity of INTRAW, brings its expertise in foresight and technological road-mapping.

MRP located in South Africa, brings in its expertise in the field of mining software that is focused on digitization in various mining related processes. Their MineRP platform is the world's only operation technology platform that is focused on unifying operation technology, geoscience, and enterprise resource planning domains in the global mining industry, hence leading the way for developing innovative sustainable comprehensive geoscience-based digital mining solutions. This digital integration is underpinned by industry strength analytical, simulation and scenario planning technology already in use in the market.

SPE is a private SME located in The Netherlands, that will participate with its unique specialization for non-contact chemical analysis using optical sensors which will be very useful in this project for in-situ ore composition analysis. It will bring its unique knowledge of applying the LIBS technology to the consortium. For more than 8 years, SPE is developing LIBS solutions for mining companies and mining equipment suppliers The research and development centre.

KGHM is a Polish mining company, who are among the world leaders in the copper and silver production while providing their expertise in the exploration, drilling, and excavation aspect withing the project. The expertise of all the partners covers all the spectrum of required multidisciplinary research contributions, while the existing complementarities ensure all the knowledge interfaces.

GSB research centre will bring its key incites from geoscientific expertise in form of geological research, mapping, monitoring activities, and technological development for spectral, geochemical and geophysical sensor.

CUP located in Poland, will provide key competence in exploration mining specifically in terms of developing sustainable, new adaptive and optimal exploitation methods in already existing excavated areas/ constrained exploitation conditions.

DTU will participate with the Department of Electrical Engineering, which has long experience in mechatronic development and control.

UPAT will participate with the Department of Mechanical Engineering that has long experience in designing novel robotic concepts and robotized machines. Their participation will focus on autonomy tasks, as well as in simulating realistically the operations in a mining environment. UPAT will also contribute on concepts about the design for the mining machines of the future.

3.2 Objectives of the DC strategy

The dissemination and communication strategy for the findings and results of the PERSEPHONE project pursues the following objectives:

- Disseminate the results to stakeholders outlined in the GA for further R&D&I activities.
- Communicate the importance and relevance of PERSEPHONE, its outputs and expected wider effects in terms of how innovative an environmentally friendly, safe, intelligent and resource efficient

extraction technologies can spur industrial leadership, enhanced sustainability, and resilience.

3.3 Target groups

A detailed categorisation of the target audience is carried out to structure the communication and dissemination activities and to analyse the impact of these activities. The current and future stakeholders who could benefit from PERSEPHONE will have access to the main results and support the exploitation.

3.3.1 Expected impact

The PERSEPHONE project proposal outlines the anticipated impact on specific target groups, as listed in Table 2. To engage these audiences more effectively, refined and detailed messages will be crafted throughout the project.

Table 2: Expected impact for target groups of the PERSEPHONE project

Target group	Expected impact
Industrial project partners	Successful project, economic exploitation
Scientific project partners	Successful project, scientific output, competence increase, cooperation with industries
Other industry (Machine manufacturers, suppliers of automation solutions and robotics), industrial associations	Encouragement of other industrial players to implement PERSEPHONE approach, thus increasing use of autonomy solutions in the safe and sustainable exploration and extraction of deep minerals deposits while lowering environmental and resource impact (win-win business)
Scientific community	Creation of new knowledge and understanding of innovative, autonomous and safe deep mineral exploration and extraction methods, digital twin of mines, as well as new research opportunities
Regional / national authorities	Ensure replication of PERSEPHONE solutions and widen the awareness of sustainable mining practices to assist the EU mining industry in reaching the green transition by minimising the costs and waste in deep-mining operations, while also trying to achieve zero human presence in high-risk zones.
Policy makers and standardization bodies	
Media	Increasing awareness on benefits of the research and innovation for increasing the sustainability and the competitiveness of the EU mining industry
Employees of project partners	Involve in DC measures
Society (public, local neighbours)	Enhanced awareness of a necessity to develop sustainable mining practices to assist the EU mining industry in reaching the green transition goals.
European Commission (EC)	Enhanced contribution to the goals of the Green Deal Industrial Plan by implementing the Critical Raw Materials Act, alongside the EU Raw Materials Initiative.
Other European partnerships	Cooperation e.g., with The European Federation of Geologists (EFG), Global Mining Guidelines Group, OECD Mining Regions and Cities and ICMM, International Council on Mining and Metals.

3.3.2 Initial key messages

For the PERSEPHONE project, initial key messages (WHAT) for specific target groups (WHO) have been defined in the proposal and are listed in Table 3. To address the specific audiences more precisely, refined and detailed messages will be developed during the project.

Table 3: PERSEPHONE key messages for specific target group

Target group	Key messages
Industrial project partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All project deliverables • Details to specific solutions (in terms of function and impact on the production process) • Project working progress (best practices, methods, concepts, issues, solutions)
Scientific project partners	
Other industry (EU miners, machine manufacturers, suppliers of automation solutions and robotics), industrial associations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information on innovative mining processes, machines, drills, sensors, and autonomy solutions • Application of sensor techniques in ore detection and mineral exploration and characterization
Scientific community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Report on dissemination and communication activities • Comparison with state-of-the-art solutions
Regional / national authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance to searching, extraction, beneficiation, and processing of valuable minerals and other geological materials • KPI's and LCA / LCC results • Potential for green transition
Policy makers and standardization bodies	
Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance of autonomy, sensor technology for future mineral extraction processes • Dissemination and communication activities
Employees of project partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impact on green transition, robotization and digitization in mining • KPI's and LCA / LCC results • Details on Exploitation and transferability • Dissemination and communication activities
Society (public, local neighbours)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance to sustainable extraction, exploration, and processing of valuable minerals and other geological materials • Sustainable mining practices potential
European Commission (EC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential to develop new pioneering technologies for sustainable mining practices • Information on mining autonomy, digitization of mines, sensor technology for future mineral extraction processes • KPI's and LCA / LCC results

Other European partnerships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Topics requiring additional expert knowledge (opportunities for cooperation) • Challenges and open issues • Dissemination activities
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3.4 Dissemination and communication channels, tools and activities

Depending on the audience different channels are used to disseminate and communicate the findings and results of the PERSEPHONE project. Figure 3 displays an organigram of those tools and lists examples of the respective categories. Scientific platforms include papers, participation in conferences, exhibition fairs and open innovation events and science popularization events. All subcategories list examples of ways to participate. The events, meetings and activities are divided into organization of workshops and meetings with the scientific advisory board. Press release and media coverage comprise the publishing in magazines and newspapers and online press releases. Social media and visual identity involve project logo and visual identity, information on project web page, creating newsletters, media channels of partners and popular social networks. The category other materials covers creating video content, timeline infographic, brochures as well as reports and documentation.

Various activities, channels and instruments come into operation for communication and dissemination. They are described in the sub-sections.

3.4.1 Unified visual identity

The PERSEPHONE logo was created during the project execution phase and is displayed in Figure 1. To provide a unified brand identity across all communication and dissemination tools, the logo is and will be used in all documentation, promotional material, and tools (electronic or paper).

Figure 1: PERSEPHONE project logo

The colour codes and their part in the logo are listed in Table 4.

Table 4: Colour codes of the PERSEPHONE project logo

Colour	Code		
	rgb(193, 211, 237)	hsl(215, 55%, 84%)	Hex: #c1d3ed
	rgb(158, 184, 224)	hsl(216, 52%, 75%)	Hex: #9eb8e0
	rgb(132, 184, 227)	hsl(207, 63%, 70%)	Hex: #84b8e3
	rgb(73, 127, 193)	hsl(213, 49%, 52%)	Hex: #497fc1
	rgb(73, 127, 193)	hsl(213, 49%, 52%)	Hex: #497fc1

3.4.2 Project presentation template

To provide unified presentations at the kick-off meeting and throughout the project, a presentation template was created and shared with all partners at the beginning of the project. Figure 2 displays the first slide of this template.

Figure 2: PowerPoint presentation template for PERSEPHONE

3.4.3 Web page

The PERSEPHONE online presence offers essential information about the project, enhancing visibility for this research area. The website provides details on project goals, recent updates, achievements, workflow, and timeline, with regular updates on ongoing progress. Beyond project partners, it targets a broad audience, including society, media, industry groups, the European Commission, regional and national authorities, policymakers, standardization bodies, and other European partnerships.

The project webpage can be visited at <https://www.persephone-mining.eu/> and imparts the following content to the visitors:

- Details of the project,
- Description of all partners involved,

- Address and contact details,
- Recent updates on the project,
- Events organised as part of the project,
- News about publishing the results in articles or at conferences,
- Public deliverables,
- Acknowledgement and reference to the Horizon Europe framework programme of the European Union.

3.4.4 Social media

LinkedIn account for PERSEPHONE has been launched and as of now (Dec 2024) it reached 109 followers. The account is accessible through the link [PERSEPHONE Mining](https://www.linkedin.com/company/persephone-mining/).

The screenshot shows the LinkedIn profile for PERSEPHONE Mining. The profile picture is a blue and white logo with the word 'PERSEPHONE' below it. The cover image shows a dark, industrial mining tunnel with a bright light source in the distance. The profile name is 'PERSEPHONE Mining' and the bio reads: 'Autonomous Exploration and Extraction of Deep Mineral Deposits - research project funded by Horizon Europe GA 101138451'. Below the bio, it says 'Research Services · 109 followers · 5K-10K employees'. There are three buttons: 'Message', 'Following', and a three-dot menu. The navigation bar shows 'Home', 'About', 'Posts', 'Jobs', and 'People'. The 'Overview' section contains a detailed description of the project's goals and funding.

PERSEPHONE Mining
Autonomous Exploration and Extraction of Deep Mineral Deposits - research project funded by Horizon Europe GA 101138451
Research Services · 109 followers · 5K-10K employees

Message Following

Home **About** Posts Jobs People

Overview

PERSEPHONE is aiming to address these challenges by developing of the pioneering technologies for pushing the limits of EU mining industry and embodiment of autonomous and integrated near mine exploration capability to access deep deposits of critical raw materials through hard-to-reach deep and abandoned mines. The overall concept and vision of PERSEPHONE will be achieved by reducing the size of mining machines currently adapted to the human scale and embedding autonomy for risk-aware navigation and full digitalization of the extraction process by digital twin creation and key enabling technologies validation at TRL 5. Additionally, PERSEPHONE is introducing completely novel approaches in online near mine exploration core analysis and overall integration of related data analytics to the mine expansion. Thus, PERSEPHONE allows to foster green transition by reducing the cost and waste generated from deep-mining operations and foster the vision of zero human presence in highly hazardous areas. These will allow to achieve PERSEPHONE's overall goal to digitalize and automate extraction value chain by creation of new concepts of energy-efficient autonomous drilling machines with advanced perception capabilities for navigation, face drilling, and core extraction, which will enable data-driven digital twin creation and geological modelling for further enhanced decision support and optimal extraction planning.

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Website
<https://www.persephone-mining.eu/>

Twitter (X) account for PERSEPHONE has been launched. To follow it use X handle **@PersephoneEU**.

3.4.5 Printed promotional materials

An official set of printed promotional materials will be developed in the project. As a part, has been developed project's leaflet shown below.

PERSEPHONE

A research and innovation project with a 3 years duration, focusing on developing pioneering technologies for pushing the limits in EU underground mining industry.

PERSEPHONE will validate an integrated autonomous mine exploration concept at TRL 5, targeted for deep and abandoned mines. The demonstrated technology will autonomously create an online digital twin of the difficult to reach mine areas, the mineralization's, and the ore deposit. The detected CRM resources will be presented according to UNFC and in line with the Critical Raw Material Act.

PERSEPHONE will contribute in:

- ROBOTICS AND AUTONOMY
- NOVEL CONCEPTS OF EXPLORATION MACHINES
- DATA INTEGRATION, INTEROPERABILITY & UNFC
- AI DATA DRIVEN MODELLING IN-SITU SENSING

Funded by the European Union
Grant agreement ID: 101138451

PERSEPHONE Project partners

- LULEÅ UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY
- DTU Technical University of Denmark
- Epiroc
- GRECIAN MAGNESITE
- Intraw
- KGHM CUPRUM
- KGHM
- LPRC L. PALMA RESEARCH CENTRE
- MineRP (Powered by Epiroc)
- natural sciences .be
- SPECTRAL INDUSTRIES
- UNIVERSITY OF PATRAS

- Conceptual machine design and technologies for coreless coring
- Eliminates need for remote connection to the surface
- Continuously creates a digital twin of the mineralization that expands over time
- High precision mining for reducing waste and environmental footprint
- Enhanced decision support for investments and future extraction development

Scan here for more info

Coordinator:
Prof. George Nikolakopoulos
geonik@ltu.se

Additionally, NFC plate has also been developed, see below.

3.4.6 Newsletter

Newsletter 1 has been released. Link to [Newsletter 1](#).

3.4.7 Shared repository

The coordinator has set up a Teams/SharePoint platform to streamline communication among project partners, accessible only to their employees. This platform enhances document sharing and transparency across activities,

providing a space for templates, deliverables, work package documents, meeting information, and more.

3.4.8 Dissemination and communication tools

The PERSEPHONE project employs diverse channels to communicate findings and results, adapted to different audiences. Figure 3 displays an organigram of those tools and lists examples of the respective categories. Scientific dissemination includes publishing papers, attending conferences, participating in exhibitions, open innovation events, and science popularization efforts, with specific participation methods outlined in each category.

Project partners will showcase the project at key national and international forums to share outcomes, engage stakeholders, and build strong connections with relevant networks, associations, and related initiatives. To maximize impact, the project leverages online platforms, scientific and technical publications, a final conference, workshops, media outreach, informational leaflets and posters, collaboration with other projects, and social and professional networking.

Figure 3 Overview of the DC tools used in the PERSEPHONE project

4 Plan for dissemination and communication

The DC objectives are outlined to organize the activities effectively. This general plan establishes key concepts and serves as a living document, continuously updated and monitored.

4.1 Schedule of DC actions

The preliminary concept for the general dissemination and communication plan was developed prior to the project's launch (see Table 5). For each project year, as well as the post-project phase, specific objectives are set, with a range of methods employed to achieve them.

Table 5: General DC plan of the PERSEPHONE project up to M36 (will be updated in the next version)

Time period	Objective	Method
M1-12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Creating a visual identity and project brand story ▪ Raising awareness on project's objectives ▪ Sharing first project results ▪ Uptake of stakeholder engagement ▪ Cooperation with other European partnerships (e.g, P4P) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Web page, social media, preliminary promotion material (flyers, brochures, leaflets) ▪ Promotion and dissemination in strategic networks of the project partners ▪ Attendance in conferences, trade fairs and seminars ▪ Newsletters to stakeholders
M12 – M36	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪

4.2 Plan for the DC activities from M1 to M12

In the first year, the project's activities will primarily focus on raising awareness about the PERSEPHONE project. This will be achieved through regular website updates, social media posts, newsletters, and the distribution of flyers and brochures. Additionally, the project team will participate in conferences, exhibitions, fairs, and seminars. Details on the activities and participating partners can be found in Table 6.

Table 6: Planned and completed PERSEPHONE activities

Date	Event	Partner	Place	Reach
March 3-6, 2024	PDAC 2024	LTU, EPI	Toronto, Canada	International
22- 26 April 2024	Hannover Messe 2024	LTU	Hannover, Germany	International
26th August 2024	37th International Geological Congress (IGC) in Busan, Korea Session S1 under the Theme 12 - Resource Prospecting of Critical	INTRAW	Busan, Korea	International

	Metals and Economic Processing			
23rd October 2024	8th MINEX Europe Forum, “Securing Europe’s metals and minerals supply”, 22-23 October 2024, Prague, Czech Republic Session 7: Revolutionising the Mining Industry operational models with new technologies	INTRAW	Prague, Czech Republic	International
31st October 2024	Digital Tech Summit	DTU	Copenhagen, Denmark	International
09-13 December 2024	Raw Materials Week (RMW) 2024	LTU, INTRAW	Brussels, Belgium	International
March 2-5, 2025	PDAC 2025	LTU	Toronto, Canada	International
27 April-2 May 2025	EGU General Assembly 2025	GSB	Vienna, Austria	International
22-24 October 2025	20th IFAC Symposium on Control, Optimization and Automation in Mining, Minerals and Metal Processing (MMM 2025)	LTU	Lima, Peru	International

Figure 4 shows a segmentation of the project duration into quarters. The requirements from the grant agreement, such as quarterly consortium meetings (four times per year), advisory board meetings (three meetings throughout the duration of the project), periodic reports are included, and colour coded. In the kick-off meeting, the project partners agreed on the publication of newsletters and press releases twice a year, and social media releases four times a year. The colour highlighting of the journal papers and patents serve as a first idea and as an indication in which work package and in which quarter results and findings could be published. As this is a living document, the entries of journal papers, patents, conference papers, industrial fairs, guided tours, and workshops are updated regularly.

DC measure	DC tool	2024				2025				2026				
		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	
Meetings	Consortium Steering Committee		C		C		C		C		C		C	
	Advisory board	SC	SC	SC	SC	SC	SC	SC	SC	SC	SC	SC	SC	
Events	Workshops	W				W		W						
	All scientific events				IF									
Reports	Report and documentation						IR			IR			FR	
Social media and press	Newsletters		NL		NL		NL		NL		NL		NL	
	Press-release	PR		PR		PR		PR		PR		PR		
	Social media coverage	SM	SM	SM	SM	SM	SM	SM	SM	SM	SM	SM	SM	
Scientific and D&C	Journals, publications, conferences, patents	WP	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
		T2.1												
		T2.2												
		T2.3						JP						
		T2.4						JP						
		T2.5												
		T3.1												
		T3.2												
		T3.3												P
		T4.1						JP						
		T4.2						JP						
		T4.3						JP						
		T4.4						JP						
		T4.5						JP						
		T5.1												
		T5.2									JP			
		T5.3												
		T5.4								JP				
		T5.5												
		T6.1												
		T6.2							JP					
		T7.1									JP			
		T7.2												
		T7.3									JP			
		T7.4									JP			
		T8.1							JP					
		T8.2							JP					
		T9.1												JP
		T9.2												
		T9.3												JP
		T9.4												
		T9.5												JP
T10.1														
T10.2														
T10.3														
T11.1														
T11.2														
T11.3														
T11.4														
T11.5														
WP12														
WP13														

- C Consortium meeting
- SC Steering Committee meeting
- AB Advisory board
- W Workshop
- IR Interim report
- FR Final Report
- NL Newsletter
- PR Press-release
- HP Homepage
- SM Social Media
- JP Journal Paper
- CP Conference paper
- P Patents
- IF Industrial fairs
- GT Guided tours
- CP Commercialization p...

Figure 4 Schedule for dissemination and communication activities

5 Dissemination management and evaluation

Throughout the project's duration, a series of reports on the DC Plan are scheduled, as detailed in Table 1. The DC activities will be regularly evaluated to assess their impact and refine future actions. Establishing a consistent visual identity for all internal and external dissemination activities is crucial. Additionally, all publications released within the framework of the PERSEPHONE project must clearly associate with PERSEPHONE and acknowledge EC funding.

5.1.1 Common visual identity

Establishing a consistent graphic identity enhances the visibility and recognition of the PERSEPHONE project. Therefore, all internal and external dissemination activities and tools should incorporate or reference the following elements:

- the project title,
- the URL of the PERSEPHONE website,
- the project logo and
- references to the EC public funding.

5.1.2 Acknowledgements and disclaimer

All publications resulting from work funded by the European Commission under the PERSEPHONE Project must acknowledge their affiliation with PERSEPHONE and recognize EC funding. The mandatory EU emblem, along with the specified acknowledgment sentence, must be included in the dissemination of project results. This requirement applies to all forms of publication, including electronic formats such as scientific papers and articles.

Figure 5: Acknowledgement of the funding by the European Union

It is mandatory that every publication and presentation is endorsed with a disclaimer, the text of which reads as follows:

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

5.2 Evaluation of the DC plan

To evaluate the effectiveness of the DC activities, key performance indicators (KPIs) have been introduced, as detailed in Table 7. Each KPI has a specific target

to be achieved by the end of the respective reporting period. By regularly monitoring these KPIs, the impact of the DC initiatives can be accurately measured

Table 7: KPI for visibility of the project and target audience

Communication instrument	When	Target audience	Evaluation and target KPIs
Visual identity	Ready by M6	Support other activities	Created project visual identity, including logo etc,
Brochures, posters, presentations	First versions of the materials created by M6 and updated throughout the project as needed.	Potential customers, end users	Min 5 posters / flyers.
Project & partner websites	Ready by M12 and updated throughout the project duration. The website will be maintained for 2 years after the project ends.	Groups A to F, including general public	Project website created and updated throughout the project to include the latest news about the project and its results. Target: 5000 visits / year.
Press releases	Throughout the project duration.	Groups A to F, including general public	Project stories and progress updates. Min. 10 during the project.
Social media	Throughout the project duration.	Groups A to F, including general public	Project presence on X and LinkedIn, with regular (min. 60) updates about its proceedings and results
Films	Throughout the project duration.	Groups A to F, including general public	Min 20 films showcasing project achievements and results viewed at least 10 000 times by M36
Newsletter	Throughout the project duration.	Groups A to F, including general public	Project newsletter min. 2 per year during the project, including the latest news about the

			project and its results
Scientific publications	Throughout the project duration.	Group C	Presentation of project results in at least 20 publications by M36
Educational modules	Throughout the project duration.	Group C	The project will result in at least 4 educational modules by M36
Other media: Media releases, interviews, white papers, case studies	Throughout the project duration.	Groups A to F	Presentation of project progress and results at least in 20 publications / news pieces
Events participation (Conference/Seminar/Fair/Tradeshaw etc.)	Throughout the project duration starting from the second year.	Group C and D	Communication of progress and results in relevant events. ≥ 20 / year starting on the second year.
Direct contacts with potential customers	Throughout the project duration.	Potential customers	Company partners 1-5 new contacts / year
Technology platforms and clusters	Throughout the project duration.	Group C and D	Participation in events and workshops, min. 10 / year
Standardisation bodies	Throughout the project duration.	Group C and D	Participation in working groups, min. 1 / year

6 Conclusions

This document provides a comprehensive overview of the PERSEPHONE project's dissemination and communication plan. As a dynamic and evolving document, it will be reviewed and updated at regular intervals to ensure its relevance and effectiveness.

In this version, we introduce the planned activities for the project, including an initial schedule for social media publications, press releases, and newsletters. These activities are designed to maximize the project's visibility and engagement with its target audience.